

Intellectual property receipts as a percentage of total trade

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The variable "intellectual property receipts as a percentage of total trade" represents the proportion of revenues generated from intellectual property (IP) in relation to a country's total trade. This metric indicates how much income related to the granting of intellectual property rights, such as patents, trademarks, copyrights, and other forms of technological or creative innovations, contributes to overall commercial exchanges. Intellectual property receipts include amounts received from both national and foreign entities for the use of exclusive rights on products, technologies, or protected works. Total trade, meanwhile, is composed of the sum of exports and imports of goods and services. Therefore, this variable helps determine the relative weight of transactions related to intellectual property within a country's overall trade. The importance of this variable lies in the fact that it reflects an economy's level of dependence on sectors driven by innovation and creativity, as opposed to the significance of traditional or tangible goods and services. In countries with industries strongly based on advanced technologies or creative content, such as those dominating the information technology, pharmaceutical, or entertainment sectors, a high percentage of intellectual property receipts compared to total trade is an indicator of greater competitiveness in high-value-added sectors. Conversely, a lower percentage might indicate less emphasis on innovation and an economy more concentrated on traditional productive sectors. This variable is particularly relevant in the context of modern, globalized economies where intellectual property has become a fundamental resource for economic growth, international competitiveness, and technological development. The data refers to the period from 2016 to 2022.

Intellectual property receipts as a percentage of total trade in 2022 highlight a highly diversified global economic landscape. At the top of the rankings are the Netherlands, with a percentage of 100%, followed by Switzerland (92.4%) and Japan (83.8%). These figures suggest that in these economies, intellectual property plays a fundamental role in their total trade, highlighting their strong reliance on sectors with high levels of innovation and creativity. The Netherlands, for example, boasts a highly advanced economic system with substantial investments in research and development (R&D), technology, and an innovation-friendly environment, which can explain the central importance of intellectual property in their trade. Switzerland, known for its pharmaceutical and technological sectors, and Japan, a global leader in the production of advanced technologies and patents, are among the economies most dependent on innovation. The United States, with a percentage of 76.2%, demonstrates how even a large and diversified economy like the U.S. is heavily influenced by intellectual property. The dominant role of the technology, pharmaceutical, and entertainment industries in the U.S. supports this figure, confirming that patents, trademarks, and copyrights represent a crucial component of total trade. Countries like Malta (73%), Iceland (71.9%), Sweden (67.3%), and Finland (65.6%) follow a similar model, showing that smaller economies with high technological content greatly benefit from the protection and export of intellectual property. Further

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down the rankings, Ireland, with 61.2%, and the United Kingdom, with 58.3%, demonstrate the importance of the creative, technological, and pharmaceutical industries in the trade of these nations. Ireland, in particular, hosts many multinational technology companies that use the country as a base for research and development operations, generating significant intellectual property revenues. The UK, with a long tradition of creativity, innovation, and a solid financial and technological sector, sees intellectual property as having a strong influence on its trade. Germany, despite being one of the world's largest industrial economies, has a value of 52%, indicating a balance between industrial production and technological innovation. An interesting aspect is seen in Northern European countries such as Denmark (50.5%) and France (47%), which highlight the importance of intellectual property in sectors such as design, technology, and research. These countries, known for their high standards of living and strong investments in innovative sectors, show significant participation of intellectual property in total trade. However, as we move further down the rankings, a gradual decline in the percentage of intellectual property receipts is seen in Eastern European, African, and Latin American countries. Italy, for instance, with 25.5%, shows a lower percentage compared to many other European countries. Despite being globally renowned for its design, fashion, and industrial production, this percentage suggests that Italian trade does not rely as heavily on intellectual property. The manufacturing and agricultural sectors, still very strong, represent a significant portion of trade, reducing the relative weight of patents and trademarks in the overall calculation. In Latin American and African countries, the values decrease further. Argentina, for example, has a percentage of 14.1%, while Brazil, one of the region's largest economies, stands at 10.5%. This may reflect the economic structure of these nations, where the production of primary goods and the agricultural sector still play a predominant role in international trade, and where technological innovation and intellectual property protection have not yet reached the same level of importance as in more developed countries. In Africa, the data reveals even lower percentages. Countries such as Kenya (16.3%), Ghana (22.6%), and Uganda (6.4%) show that trade in these nations still heavily relies on natural resources and traditional goods, with a limited impact from intellectual property. This is not surprising, considering that many African economies are still in the developmental phase and have limited technological innovation capabilities. However, it is worth noting that there are signs of growth in certain areas, particularly in sectors such as telecommunications and information technology, which could, in the future, increase the importance of intellectual property in these regions. Another significant aspect emerges from the data on major emerging economies such as China (10.8%), India (7.1%), and Russia (10.1%). These countries, which have made enormous strides in economic growth, show that intellectual property has not yet taken on a central role in their trade. Despite China being a technological and industrial powerhouse today, its relatively low percentage can be explained by its historical reliance on low-cost industrial models and mass production of goods, although the country is now working to enhance the protection and utilization of intellectual property. The same applies to India, where the services sector and the pharmaceutical industry are growing, but intellectual property-related trade has not yet reached the level seen in more developed economies. In conclusion, the variable concerning the percentage of intellectual property receipts relative to total trade highlights a clear division between highly developed economies, which heavily rely on intellectual property to support their trade, and less developed economies, where technological innovation and intellectual property protection still play a marginal role. In countries with mature economies, such as the Netherlands, Switzerland, and Japan, intellectual property is a crucial driver of economic growth. In contrast, in many emerging and developing economies, trade structures remain heavily tied to the production of traditional goods and the sale of natural resources. However, with growing globalization and the spread of technologies, more countries are likely to seek to increase their

contribution to intellectual property-related trade by investing in innovation, research, and development.

Intellectual property receipts as a percentage of total trade between 2016 and 2022. The data on the percentage and absolute variations of intellectual property receipts in relation to total trade between 2016 and 2022 provide an interesting snapshot of global economic dynamics related to intellectual property (IP). Some countries have registered impressive increases in IP receipts relative to total trade, while others have experienced significant declines, highlighting various economic factors, government policies, and technological investments. A striking example is Cyprus, which saw an extraordinary increase from 2016 to 2022, with a rise of 41.9 percentage points, representing growth of 2992.86%. This exceptional increase could be attributed to the country's economic transformation, where Cyprus has become a hub for international companies, attracting investments in sectors such as technology, finance, and innovation. Uruguay followed a similar trend, with an increase of 2566.67%, rising from 0.3% to 8%. Although the absolute value remains relatively low, the leap is notable and suggests a shift in the country's economic structure, likely tied to a greater focus on technological innovation and the creation of a more favorable environment for IP-focused companies. Cameroon, with a growth of 1900%, and Albania, with an increase of 1542.86%, show that even emerging or less developed economies are slowly increasing their capacity to generate revenue through intellectual property. These countries may have adopted policies aimed at encouraging innovation or attracting foreign investments, thus increasing the role of IP in their total trade. The growth of African economies like Cameroon can be seen as a positive sign of greater economic diversification, especially considering the historical importance of sectors such as agriculture and mining. Another noteworthy case is China, which saw an increase of 671.43% in intellectual property receipts, rising from 1.4% to 10.8%. This result reflects China's extraordinary technological progress in recent decades. The Chinese government has heavily invested in research and development, promoting strategic sectors such as artificial intelligence, robotics, and renewable energy. Consequently, China has emerged as one of the world's leading powers in intellectual property, with an increasingly significant impact on global trade. Bangladesh and Ethiopia, with increases of 300% each, also indicate signs of progress in their respective economic contexts. However, the absolute values remain low, suggesting that these economies are still in the early stages of developing their capacity to generate IP revenue. These countries could benefit from further investments in education, technological infrastructure, and policies aimed at protecting and promoting innovation. On the other side of the spectrum, some countries have experienced significant decreases in IP receipts relative to total trade. The most dramatic decline was recorded in Rwanda, with a drop of 99.47%, falling from 94.5% in 2016 to 0.5% in 2022. This extraordinary decline could result from structural changes in the country's economy, which may have shifted its focus toward other forms of trade or faced setbacks due to internal or external factors such as political or economic instability. Other countries that experienced significant declines include Yemen (-95.68%), Madagascar (-80.75%), and El Salvador (-84.47%). These drastic declines could be attributed to a combination of factors, including internal conflicts, economic crises, or a lack of investment in the intellectual property sector. In Europe, even highly developed countries such as Switzerland, Finland, and Sweden have seen notable decreases in their percentages of IP receipts relative to total trade. Switzerland, which had a percentage of 100% in 2016, saw a decline of 7.6% in 2022, reaching 92.4%. While this decline seems relatively moderate in percentage terms, it still suggests a shift in Switzerland's trade dynamics, perhaps due to increased global competition or a drop in IP exports. Sweden and Finland experienced steeper declines of 32.7% and 34.4%, respectively, both falling from 100% to lower percentages. In these cases as well, the decrease may reflect greater international competition or reduced investments in research and development. The case of the United States deserves particular attention. The country recorded a

decline of 23.8%, falling from 100% in 2016 to 76.2% in 2022. The United States has long been a global leader in intellectual property, with major multinational technology, pharmaceutical, and entertainment companies dominating the global market. However, this decline could be attributed to various factors, including increased international competition, especially from emerging countries such as China and India, or changes in global trade policies, such as the U.S.-China trade war. Despite the decline, the United States remains one of the world's leading players in the intellectual property sector. Another important economy that experienced a significant decline is the United Kingdom, which saw a decrease of 28.82%, falling from 81.9% to 58.3%. Here too, Brexit and the associated economic uncertainties may have played a role in negatively influencing the country's ability to maintain its IP revenues. The UK has historically had a strong creative and technological sector, but its separation from the European Union may have impacted IP exports and global competitiveness. Other European countries, such as France (-29.43%), Denmark (-24.74%), and Malta (-26.19%), have registered similar declines, suggesting that although European economies remain strong in the intellectual property sector, they may have been affected by global changes in trade dynamics or increasing competition from emerging countries. In conclusion, the data shows a diversity of experiences among countries in terms of intellectual property receipts relative to total trade between 2016 and 2022. Some countries, particularly those in developing or emerging economies, have made significant progress in increasing their contribution to global trade through intellectual property, while others, including some developed countries, have seen declines in their IP revenues. This may reflect growing global competition, the constant need for innovation, and the importance of government policies aimed at supporting and protecting intellectual property.

Economic Policies. Economic policies aimed at increasing intellectual property (IP) revenues as a percentage of total trade are essential for strengthening economies based on innovation and creativity. In an increasingly technology- and knowledge-driven global context, intellectual property plays a crucial role in stimulating economic growth, boosting international competitiveness, and ensuring returns on investments in research and development (R&D). Therefore, economic policies should focus on creating a favorable environment for the creation, protection, and promotion of intellectual property, with a particular emphasis on innovation, legal protection of copyrights and patents, and incentivizing private and public investments in high-value-added sectors. A central element of economic policies for promoting IP revenues is investment in R&D. Governments should encourage both private companies and public institutions to invest in innovation through tax incentives, direct funding, and public-private partnerships. Economies that stand out for high percentages of IP revenues relative to total trade, such as Switzerland, the United States, and Japan, have historically supported R&D with active policies that facilitate the creation of new technologies, inventions, and innovative products. These policies can include R&D tax credits, which allow companies to deduct a significant portion of expenses incurred for developing new technologies or improving existing products. This type of incentive encourages companies to take more risks in research projects, increasing the likelihood of creating valuable intellectual property that can be protected through patents and then monetized. Legal protection of intellectual property rights is another fundamental pillar of economic policies in this area. Governments must ensure that their legal systems provide effective and swift protection for patents, trademarks, copyrights, and other types of intellectual property. A weak protection system can discourage innovation, as companies may hesitate to invest in new technologies if they are not confident they can protect their investments from theft or unfair competition. For this reason, many countries have reformed or improved their IP protection systems, ensuring faster patent issuance and adopting stricter legal measures against counterfeiting. In this context, international cooperation is also essential. In a global economy, innovations often spread rapidly beyond national borders, requiring countries to collaborate in harmonizing intellectual

property laws and enforcing the rights of IP holders internationally. Multilateral agreements like the TRIPS Agreement (Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights) of the World Trade Organization are examples of how countries can work together to ensure that intellectual property rights are protected globally. Additionally, governments can implement policies to promote the commercialization of intellectual property. It is not enough to create IP; it is essential to find ways to turn it into a marketable product that generates revenue. This is where the concept of technology transfer comes into play, which involves the process through which inventions and innovations created in research laboratories or universities are turned into products or services that can be sold on the market. Many governments encourage technology transfer through policies that promote collaboration between universities, research institutions, and businesses. Creating innovation ecosystems, such as technology districts or science parks, facilitates the development and commercialization of new technologies. These environments encourage collaboration between researchers, entrepreneurs, and investors, fostering the creation of innovative start-ups that can contribute to increasing IP revenues. Education and training also play a key role in sustaining long-term growth in IP revenues. Education policies should be geared towards training a highly qualified workforce capable of creating and managing intellectual property. Schools and universities must prepare young people not only in technical disciplines such as engineering, science, and computer science but also in the legal and managerial skills necessary to protect and promote intellectual property. This means training professionals who can understand the mechanisms of patent protection, copyright management, and the commercialization of IP-based products. A high-quality education focused on innovative and entrepreneurial skills helps build a solid foundation for creating valuable intellectual property, thereby strengthening the contribution of IP to a country's total trade. Another relevant aspect of economic policies to increase IP revenues is promoting IP-based exports. Countries should focus on expanding international markets for IP-based products and services. This can be achieved by opening new markets through trade agreements that include specific clauses for the protection and promotion of intellectual property and by supporting programs for companies looking to export their technologies and innovative products. Governments can also provide support to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to help them internationalize, assisting them in understanding and managing the complex intellectual property systems in foreign markets. In addition, the role of cultural and creative sectors should not be underestimated. Sectors such as film, music, publishing, and design generate a significant amount of intellectual property that can be monetized through licensing, copyrights, and international distribution agreements. Governments should therefore incentivize the growth of these sectors by offering support for intellectual property protection even in arts and culture. The entertainment industry, in particular, has demonstrated a unique ability to generate IP revenues, with a significant impact on the total trade of many countries, especially the United States. In summary, economic policies aimed at increasing intellectual property revenues as a percentage of total trade must focus on a combination of factors: promoting research and development, strengthening the legal protection of intellectual property rights, supporting the commercialization of innovations, providing education and training for a highly qualified workforce, and incentivizing the internationalization of IP-based enterprises. Only through an integrated and strategic approach can countries maximize the contribution of intellectual property to their trade and, consequently, to their economic growth. Moreover, in an increasingly interconnected and competitive world, nations that can effectively develop and protect intellectual property will be better equipped to face global economic challenges and sustain long-term growth based on innovation and creativity.

Conclusions. The value of intellectual property revenues as a percentage of total trade decreased on average between 2016 and 2022, falling from 20.05 units to 16.58 units, representing a decline of 17.29%. However, some countries saw significant increases in this value, including Cyprus with +2992.86%, Uruguay with +2566.67%, Cameroon with +1900.00%, Albania with +1542.86%, and Morocco with +800.00%. Conversely, some countries experienced a much greater decline in IP revenues as a percentage of international trade than the average between 2016 and 2022, such as Madagascar with -80.75%, El Salvador with -84.47%, Mexico with -90.00%, Yemen with -95.68%, and Rwanda with -99.47%.

Country	2016	2022	Var Ass	Var Per	Country	2016	2022	Var Ass	Var Per	Country	2016	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Cyprus	1,4	43,3	41,9	2992,86	India	5,9	7,1	1,2	20,34	Thailand	3,7	2,9	-0,8	-21,62
Uruguay	0,3	8	7,7	2566,67	Israel	25,9	31	5,1	19,69	Burkina Faso	0,9	0,7	-0,2	-22,22
Cameroon	0,1	2	1,9	1900,00	Lithuania	3,1	3,7	0,6	19,35	United States	100	76,2	-23,8	-23,80
Albania	0,7	11,5	10,8	1542,86	Cambodia	1,3	1,5	0,2	15,38	Denmark	67,1	50,5	-16,6	-24,74
Morocco	0,1	0,9	0,8	800,00	Bosnia and Herzegovina	7,4	8,5	1,1	14,86	Malta	98,9	73	-25,9	-26,19
China	1,4	10,8	9,4	671,43	Portugal	4,9	5,4	0,5	10,20	North Macedonia	7,6	5,6	-2	-26,32
Bangladesh	0,1	0,4	0,3	300,00	Luxembourg	37,6	40,7	3,1	8,24	United Kingdom	81,9	58,3	-23,6	-28,82
Ethiopia	0,2	0,8	0,6	300,00	Serbia	8,7	9,4	0,7	8,05	France	66,6	47	-19,6	-29,43
Malaysia	1,3	4,5	3,2	246,15	Indonesia	1,4	1,5	0,1	7,14	Uganda	9,2	6,4	-2,8	-30,43
Peru	0,8	2,2	1,4	175,00	Hong Kong SAR, China	4,4	4,6	0,2	4,55	Sweden	100	67,3	-32,7	-32,70
Bulgaria	4,1	10,9	6,8	165,85	Canada	32,4	32,5	0,1	0,31	Finland	100	65,6	-34,4	-34,40
Croatia	3,6	8,6	5	138,89	Algeria	0,1	0,1	0	0,00	Ukraine	8,2	5,2	-3	-36,59
Belarus	4,1	9,6	5,5	134,15	Iran, Islamic Rep.	0,6	0,6	0	0,00	Ireland	100	61,2	-38,8	-38,80
Senegal	1,5	3,2	1,7	113,33	Kazakhstan	0,1	0,1	0	0,00	Chile	4	2,3	-1,7	-42,50
Botswana	0,1	0,2	0,1	100,00	Korea, Rep.	35,1	34,9	-0,2	-0,57	Romania	7,9	4,5	-3,4	-43,04
Philippines	0,6	1,2	0,6	100,00	Czechia	14	13,3	-0,7	-5,00	Greece	7,1	4	-3,1	-43,66
Latvia	1,3	2,5	1,2	92,31	Austria	22,1	20,9	-1,2	-5,43	Georgia	0,9	0,4	-0,5	-55,56
Argentina	7,4	14,1	6,7	90,54	South Africa	4,8	4,5	-0,3	-6,25	Mauritius	1,6	0,7	-0,9	-56,25
Colombia	3,8	7,2	3,4	89,47	Kyrgyz Republic	1,4	1,3	-0,1	-7,14	Pakistan	1,4	0,6	-0,8	-57,14
Estonia	1,9	3,5	1,6	84,21	Switzerland	100	92,4	-7,6	-7,60	Hungary	83,5	34,7	-48,8	-58,44

Panama	1,4	2,5	1,1	78,57	Italy	28,1	25,5	-2,6	-9,25	Mongolia	1,7	0,7	-1	-58,82
Brazil	6	10,5	4,5	75,00	Guatemala	4,3	3,9	-0,4	-9,30	Montenegro	2,3	0,9	-1,4	-60,87
Poland	5,7	9,8	4,1	71,93	Kenya	18,3	16,3	-2	-10,93	Moldova	7,6	2	-5,6	-73,68
Russian Federation	6,1	10,1	4	65,57	Tunisia	4,9	4,3	-0,6	-12,24	Burundi	0,4	0,1	-0,3	-75,00
Slovak Republic	1,4	2,2	0,8	57,14	Belgium	33,7	28,6	-5,1	-15,13	Madagascar	21,3	4,1	-17,2	-80,75
New Zealand	26,9	40,5	13,6	50,56	Slovenia	8,9	7,5	-1,4	-15,73	El Salvador	10,3	1,6	-8,7	-84,47
Singapore	27,3	39,8	12,5	45,79	Japan	100	83,8	-16,2	-16,20	Mexico	1	0,1	-0,9	-90,00
Germany	38,3	52	13,7	35,77	Australia	13,9	11,5	-2,4	-17,27	Yemen, Rep.	18,5	0,8	-17,7	-95,68
Costa Rica	1,1	1,4	0,3	27,27	Iceland	89,1	71,9	-17,2	-19,30	Rwanda	94,5	0,5	-94	-99,47
Norway	9,8	12,3	2,5	25,51	Jamaica	5,1	4	-1,1	-21,57					

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/>

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